

Are Energy Communities actual Ostrom's institutions?

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- We are interested in analyzing the organizational model called “Energy community” through the lenses of Institutional Theory à la Elinor Ostrom.
- We are mainly interested in ECs long term survival, also with respect (if relevant) to the management model adopted.

What are Energy Communities ?

- In a broader sense, ECs are organizational structures designed to meet collective interests
- The EU has pushed and empowered local communities in the energy transition process (e.g., *Clean Energy Package* and the *European Green Deal*).

Most frequent organizational models:

- Centralized communities
- Decentralised communities (with or without P2P)
- Community of consumers
- Third-party communities
- Or a mix of the above-mentioned arrangement

Increasing role of digitalization (smart grids, smart meters, blockchain, etc..)

Energy Communities real spread

- ECs' projects are an “*emergent phenomenon*” (van der Schoor and Scholtens, 2015); actually, as organizational models
- However,
 - They are in majority, of small scale and structured as pilot projects.
 - They are developed in niches.
 - Their potential in terms of scalability and replication has yet to be exploited.
 - There are still doubts on their long-term endurance as stable models.
- The reason why ECs are not widespread seems to be mainly explained by social factors, business markets, regulations, and policies (Sokolowski, 2020; Blash et al., 2021, Antonioli Mantegazzini et al., 2022).

Do (and how) ECs deal with Commons?

- Energy provision (generation, distribution, storage) relies on the use of local, physical and non-physical infrastructures, which could be more appropriately defined as a common resource and the challenges faced in its provision are similar to common pool problems (Little 2005; Künneke & Finger 2009; Goldthau 2014; Wolsink 2020).
- There might be free riding both in consumption and production:
 - Problems of appropriations: how to divide costs and benefits deriving from commons
 - Problems of rule-making: how to define rules for ECs
 - Problems of rule-enforcing: how to enforce those rules
 - Problems of incentives: how to incentivize ECs' participants to follow collective (and not individual) interests
 - Problem of monitoring: how a group can monitor and disincentive free-riding.

- ECs are institutional arrangements to manage commons
 - In our case the commons is represented by the collective production and/or collective consumption of energy at the local level
 - And related problems
- Using Ostrom's theoretical framework (*Governing commons*), how to design and govern ECs
 - We are compiling a dataset on the goals, charters, and organizational rules of a group of ECs. Currently, our primary focus is on Italy and Ticino/Switzerland, but we are interested in expanding the collection to include other countries;
 - Very preliminary results, but interesting to address the investigation.

Principle	Application to EC
User/Resource Boundaries	Boundaries between users and nonusers are defined through technology/control of access-smart grids
Congruence with Local Conditions	Energy provision, technology and charges are in line with capabilities and needs of local users
Appropriation and Provision	Distribution of costs is proportional to the distribution of benefits (<i>but...</i>)
Collective Choice Arrangements	Users are authorized to participate in making and modifying the rules.
Monitoring User/Resource	Not clearly defined
Graduated Sanctions	Specified but not graduated; LDR
Minimal Recognition of Rights	Clearly defined in the charters
Nested Enterprises	Local energy systems are usually connected to larger distribution network and energy markets.

Conclusions and research agenda

We applied Ostrom's design principles to selected ECs case studies (in Italy, Switzerland, and France);

Preliminary results:

- In line with design principles on user and resource boundaries, collective choice arrangements, congruence with local conditions, and minimal recognition of rights;
- Not in line with:
 - Self monitoring
 - Self governance
- Concerns related to the need for collective management of public subsidies and incentives.
- Role of IT and organizational model
- Replicability?

Thank you for your attention.
Ready to collect comments and suggestions

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